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Introduction. The key to success which students is making sure they are engaged with any material they are learning. It is necessary for students to use a quality and an effective teaching methodology so that they can learn faster and understand more easily. So, in this process, Inquiry-based learning can help us. What is inquiry-based learning? Inquiry based learning (IBL) is an approach to learning that emphasizes the students role in the learning process. According to the Rachel Spronken-Smith article "Experiencing the Process of Knowledge Creation: The Nature and Use of Inquiry-Based Learning in Higher Education, Inquiry-based learning (IBL) is a pedagogy which best enables students to experience the processes of knowledge creation and the key attributes are learning stimulated by inquiry, a student-centred approach, a move to self-directed learning, and an active

IMPORTANCE OF INQUIRY-BASED LEARNING IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, I will analyze the importance of Inquiry-based learning, the elements of Inquiry-based learning (IBL), the phases of IBL process, the effectiveness of IBL.

approach to learning. Students should develop research skills and become life-long learners. There is strong educational theoretical support for the use of inquiry approaches and IBL is being adopted across the full spectrum of disciplines at all levels from within-class activities, through to inquiry courses and even inquiry degree programmes. Evidence is gradually accumulating that shows IBL can enhance student engagement, academic achievement and higher order learning outcomes [1].

Main body. I can say about the value of IBL is a process of learning that involves a number of important activities for students, including asking their own questions, investigating multiple sources of information for a purpose, thinking critically to make sense of information they have found and establishing and

communicating new understandings and knowledge. We may see that there are 5 general inquiry phases. They are: orientation, conceptualization, investigation, conclusion, discussion. I will understand all of them. Orientation is a process is a process of stimulating curiosity about topic and addressing a learning challenge through a problem statement. Conceptualization is a process of understanding a concept or concepts belonging to the stated problem. Investigation is a process of planning exploration or experimentation collecting and analyzing data based on the experimental design or exploration. Conclusion is a process drawing conclusions from the data. Comparing inferences made based on data with hypothesis or research questions. Discussion is a process of presenting findings of particular phases or the whole inquiry cycle by communicating with others and controlling the whole learning process or its phases by engaging in reflective activities [2]. I can add that about 5 elements of IBL.

1. Essential questions. The essential question also directs the course of student research. The question starts the research process. As such, essential questions are powerful, directive and commit students to the process of critical thinking through inquiry. Ultimately, the answer to the essential question will require that students craft a response that involves knowledge construction. This new knowledge building occurs through the integration of discrete pieces of information obtained during the research process. Answers to essential questions are a direct measure of student

comprehension. 2. Student Engagement. The second aspect of the Inquiry-Based Learning is Student Engagement. This focuses upon students participating in their own learning. 3. Cooperative interaction. Another element of the Inquiry-Based Learning strategy is that students create their own learning and there is a process in place for doing so. These include: Students are asked to communicate, work in pairs or groups, discussing ideas. Students are not in competition with each other. Answers may reach a "correct" answer without everyone having exactly the same product. 4. Performance evaluation. Instructors need obviously create instruction that can measure student learning. These will allow the students to demonstrate their level of understanding. 5. Variety of resources. Students use multiple resources: textbooks, web sites, videos, posters, experts, etc., to support their learning. The instructor selects these source.

Conclusion. Using inquiry-based learning to accomplish both engagement and skill-building is a popular strategy. It actively involves students in problem-solving, collaboration, and the development of skills that ready them for college and career. Inquiry-based learning lets students really explore the material, which keeps them engaged in asking questions and discussing ideas with their classmates and teacher. Students' questions create a deep level of engagement.

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